



Figure: A. *Musa siangensis* Taid, S.S. Singh & Gajurel: A1. Inflorescence with bud, A2. Fruit bunch, B. *Musa bracteata* S. S. Singh, Gajurel & Taid: B1. Inflorescence with bud, B2. Fruit bunch.